

THE PHONOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE ENGLISH SPEECH SOUNDS

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Abstract. This article is about Phonological Aspects of the English speech sounds. In the process of reading the article, What is phoneme?, What is phonology? and at the same time you will get information about phonological contrasts, phonological elements, and sounds.

Keywords: phonetic elements, phonetic units, phonology, phoneme, segmental, suprasegmental, phonological oppositions.

ФОНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЗВУКОВ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ РЕЧИ

Аннотация. Эта статья о фонологических аспектах звуков английской речи. В процессе чтения статьи Что такое фонема?, Что такое фонология? и в то же время вы получите информацию о фонологических контрастах, фонологических элементах и звуках.

Ключевые слова: фонетические элементы, фонетические единицы, фонология, фонема, сегментарное, надсегментное, фонологические оппозиции.

Any segment of a language consists of a sound chain which is distinctive through some articulatory, acoustic and perceptual features. However not all the phonetic elements characteristic to distinguish lexical and grammatical forms. Some elements serve to distinguish words, morphemes and phrases and some of them can't serve this purpose. Thus, it is the functions of distinction and also identification which is characteristic of all linguistic units. Phonetic units – syllables of sounds, characterized linguistically according to the tasks of stress and intonation and divided into certain levels, groups and subgroups. Phonology is the branch of linguistics that research how languages or dialects systematically prepare their sounds or, for signal languages, their constituent parts of signs. The term can additionally refer particularly to the sound or signal device of a precise language variety. In a broad sense phonetics includes phonology as distinct from morphology, syntax, and stylistics. But in the narrow sense, the term phonetics is used in addition to phonology. Let us talk about some simple concepts of phonology. Phonetics and phonology have two ranges of investigation: segmental and supra-segmental. Segmental phonology studies phonemes realised in a range of speech sounds. Suprasegmental phonology studies the special features realised in syllables, stress and intonation. It is handy to use the term phonemics for segmental phonology as it refers to the time period phoneme itself. As to suprasegmental phonology the term “prosodics” may be used. Thus, phonology can also be divided into phonemics and prosodics. Although these terms were recommended and grew to be famous in modern day linguistics we are the usage of them in one of a kind senses. The essential concept of phonemics is the phoneme which is the smallest unit of a language system. It is not possible to establish the precise wide variety of speech sounds but, generalizing them all we combine them into a sure variety of phonemes, which are real, and at the identical time abstract units of a language, as the language itself is an abstract phenomenon realized in the shape of speech. Thus, the dialectal unity of an abstract and concrete explains the materialistic approach to the issue of the phoneme. There are numerous phonological theories in present day linguistics. Every phonological concept suggests its private definition of the thinking

. But the time period «phoneme» itself has now no longer been changed. Among the first founders of the time duration and the thinking of such terrific linguists as I. A. Badouin de Courtenay, N.Krushevsky (Russia), P. Passy (France), H. Sweet' (England), F. De Saussure (Switzerland) and others. Phoneme is the smallest meaningless unit of a language which types and distinguishes words and morphemes. The phoneme is a minimal part which can't be divided into similarly smaller devices however for scientific analysis, it can be separated from the material form (the sound structure) of the word. Besides it exists in the structure of a quantity of articulatory and acoustically particular speech sounds, its allophones . All sounds of this variety which have common articulatory and acoustic elements represent the material in variant of the phoneme. It is due to concrete actuality that the phoneme is manifested in speech chain in its allophones which are suggested objectively and range from every other to some degree . The abstracted and generalized feature of the phoneme is reflected in its definition as a language unit . All linguistic units are formed as a result of abstraction and generalization of real speech sentences . In conventional a phoneme cannot be pronounced. We constantly pronounce one of the allophones (variants) of the phoneme then once more unconsciously generalize all the allophones as representatives of the equal phoneme . The sound /e/ has its articulatory and acoustic features as a front, half-close unrounded, short, lax vowel. But all these aspects are established as a end result of phonemic abstraction. In reality it is not possible to pronounce a sound many situations in the equal way barring changing its features. Every phoneme consists of a bundle of aspects generalized from its allophones. Contrast between speech sounds, which serves to distinguish the meanings of words, is called "Phonological Contrast".

For example:

/p-t/-pool/pu:1/- tool /tu:l/,

/l-s/-let/let/ -set/set/,

/r-l/-right/rait/ - light /lait/, etc. Words used to describe phonological contrasts are called minimal pairs of words or guasihomonyms (a term proposed by L. V. Shcherba). All the phonological contrasts are categorised into two member oppositions but the fundamental difference between the members of contrast is primarily based on the wide variety of the different features: single when there is one distinct feature (e. G. /p-t), double – when there are two unique elements (e. G. /pd/) and complex when there are greater than two special points (e. G. /pz/). There are additionally non- phonological contrasts which can't serve to distinguish words. For example, the difference between aspirated /p", t", k"/ and non-aspirated /p, t, k/ sounds is non-phonological. A function which is one of a kind in one language may additionally be non- specific in another. The thought of a specific characteristic is essential to analyze the persona of phonological contrasts . The articulatory, acoustic and perceptual characteristic which can divide into two phonemes is referred to as a one of a kind feature. The characteristic which can't serve this purpose is recognized as a non-distinctive feature. Each phoneme can be distinguished from other phonemes by this unique and ambiguous feature. Thus, a phoneme is a set of specific features. Relative to a phoneme, allophones of the same phoneme are nonspecific, for example, the relationship between /p/ aspirated and /p/ unaspirated can be characterized as nonspecific. However the frequent features of /p/ and /p/ generalize the phoneme /p/ which is bilabial, plosive-occlusive, voiceless'. Phoneme, as a linguistic unit, performs the task of distinguishing lexical and grammatical forms, and thus fulfills its communicative function in the language. Each phoneme is a member of a phonological contrast with its allophones. The exact

number of phonemes present in a particular language, also known as phoneme inventory, is determined using the commutation method. This technique is described as substitution or changing one speech sound by means of every other in the identical position of minimal pairs of words. For example: pet-bet-set-let-met-net -jet-get – vet. Sometimes it is very hard to discover minimal pairs. As in the case of /t/, /dʒ/, /θ/, // etc. It is viable to locate a few minimal pairs however no minimal pair exists for the contrast //-/θ/. But if the language does not have a minimal pair, we should not exclude the phoneme from the inventory. For example, the phoneme /ts/ in Russian and its derivative in Uzbek is not used in the minimal pair, but we describe it as a special phoneme with limited distribution. 1) If two factors cannot be used in the identical position and exchange each different in one position they are viewed to be in a complementary distribution. For example, the aspirated sounds /pʰ, tʰ, kʰ/ can be used only when there is no /s/ before stressed vowels and in the intervocalic position. However in all different positions non-aspirated /p, t, k/ sounds are used. Thus /pʰ, tʰ, kʰ/ sounds cannot substitute /p, t, k/ sounds in the identical position. They represent the allophones of the /p, t, k/ phonemes. They represent allophones of phonemes /p, t, k/. Allophones of a phoneme can be established using the complement distribution. Allophones of a phoneme can be established using the complement distribution. 2) Two factors (sounds) may be used in one and identical position and serve to distinguish the words.

For example: bill /bil/ - till /til/, sight /sait/ - bight /bant/ - night /nait/ - right /rait/ - light /lait/ might /mait/ and so on. Using the contrast distribution, it is possible to determine the number of phonemes in a given language. 3) Elements (sounds) that are used in the same situation and cannot distinguish the meaning of the word are considered freely variable. In such cases, each sound represents a free allophone of the phoneme. This type of distribution is regarded additionally as an equivalent distribution. For example, some speakers pronounce the /e/ sound as a semi-close /e/ or a semi-open /ɛ/ in the same position, but he cannot separate the words. 4) Two different sounds can be used in the same position. In such situations one of the sounds represents the free allophone of the other. For example, the word phonetics can also be pronounced as /fonetiks/, /founetiks/ and /fənetiks/ the place the sounds /o/, /ə/ symbolize the free allophones of the phoneme /ou/. In fact, each of them is an allophone of a separate phoneme. The method of distribution of sound content is very important in phonological analysis. It is fundamental to show also what clusters of sounds the sample of a language admits. It is also necessary to indicate what clusters of sounds the language pattern accepts. The branch of phonology that studies the possible clusters of sounds in words and morphemes is called "phonotactics". Using the statistical method, it is possible to determine the exact number of phonological contrasts in the language and the number of sound clusters in the initial, medial and final positions of words. According to statistics, it is possible to determine the exact number of phonological contrasts in the language and the number of sound clusters in the initial, medial and final positions of words. For example, in English, only 40 out of 11,000 theoretically possible initial three-member consonant clusters occur at the beginning of a syllable. Of the 576 possible combinations of two consonants, only 137 are used in the language.

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